

The impact of structured physical activity on metabolic health outcomes in people with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: a systematic review.

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Abstract

This dissertation presents secondary research in the form of a systematic review of recent literature examining the effectiveness of physical activity in managing Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). Currently, it is a global concern associated with high levels of morbidity, mortality and economic burden. Structural physical activity with guidelines from the World Health Organisation and other institutions states that aerobic, resistance and combined training have been recognised as vital non-pharmacological interventions to improve glycemic control and metabolic health outcomes in people affected by Type 2 Diabetes.

A comprehensive search strategy was conducted across five academic databases - PubMed, SportDiscus, Cochrane Library, Google Scholar and BASE - in order to identify relevant peer-reviewed studies published between 2015 and 2025. After applying inclusion and exclusion criteria and conducting quality appraisal using the AMSTAR 2 tool, eight studies were included in the final review.

The findings confirm that structural physical activity intervention can lead to massive improvements in HbA1C level, insulin sensitivity, and overall metabolic outcomes. Combined modalities of aerobic and resistance training programs were particularly effective in achieving expected changes. In addition, strategies of behavioural support and digital health tools were proven to enhance adherence levels and long-term engagement. The review highlights the existing need for more personalised exercise protocols and integrated lifestyle approaches that include psychological, behavioural and nutritional support. Integration of physical activity as a core component is supported as a method of managing T2DM and calls for expanded clinical and public health strategies that promote exercise interventions for long-term metabolic health.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background & Context

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder which is characterised by hyperglycemia, insulin resistance and impaired beta-cell function (Low *et al*, 2025). It is an existing major global health problem with the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimating that around 540 million people worldwide are affected, with the number projected to rise to 784 million by the year 2045 (IDF, 2024). T2DM is, according to Karami *et al*, (2021), associated with many severe complications, including neuropathy, retinopathy, and cardiovascular and kidney failure, leading to an increased mortality rate. These T2DM complications are affecting the quality of life of a person and place a substantial economic burden on healthcare systems worldwide (Trikkalinou *et al*, 2017)

A person's lifestyle choices, including sedentary behaviour, poor dietary habits and obesity, are one of the major contributors to the development and progression of T2DM and obesity. According to studies, this has become a global pandemic in the last 20 years, contributing to the development of the disorder. (Ruze *et al*, 2023). While the pharmacological interventions, as stated by Molugulu *et al*, (2017), like insulin therapy, metformin, and sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitors, help in glycemic control. However, the evidence presented suggests that non-traditional and non-pharmacological approaches, especially structured physical activity, can offer significant metabolic benefits while reducing dependence on medication (Colberg *et al*, 2016).

The statement published by Kanaley *et al*, (2022) suggests that regular physical exercise can prevent and delay the disorder and resistance training resulting in around a 15% increase in strength, blood pressure and muscle mass in people affected by T2DM. Avery *et al*, (2015) said exercise improves glucose uptake, lipid metabolism, and insulin sensitivity and lowers oxidative stress and systemic inflammation, factors associated with diabetic progression (Bennetsen *et al*, 2020).

1.2 The Role of Physical Activity in T2DM Management

Physical activity is recognised as an important non-pharmacological strategy to manage T2DM. Research conducted by Whelan *et al*, (2019) produced evidence that structured exercise programs, including resistance training, aerobic exercise and combined modalities, can improve insulin sensitivity, lower HbA1C levels and significantly improve cardiovascular health. Additionally, the publication of Nery *et al*, (2017) suggests that moderate aerobic exercises like walking, running or cycling can

decrease blood glucose levels and improve the cardiovascular system. Resistance training contributes to muscle growth and the level of muscle glucose uptake and insulin sensitivity, positively influencing glycemic control. Further research by AL-Mhanna *et al*, (2024) indicates that combining resistance and aerobic training can benefit a person affected by diabetes. Both modalities are shown to improve glycemic control more effectively than a single modality. Explanation for this is that aerobic exercises, as stated by Kobayashi *et al*, (2023), work mainly on the cardiovascular system of the body and fat oxidation, whereas resistance training stimulates muscle hypertrophy and increases the storage capacity of glucose and metabolic rate.

The World Health Organisation recommends at least 150 minutes of moderate-level physical activity per week, followed by two or more days of strength training for optimal metabolic benefit (Kahlmeier *et al*, 2015). However, as stated by the World Health Organisation (2024), only 31% of adults and 80% of the adolescent population worldwide do not follow the guideline. A clinical trial conducted by Mukherji *et al*, (2022) stated that about 38% of adults affected by T2DM have less than 10 minutes of physical activity a week, citing factors like lack of time and motivation, physical limitations or being afraid of hypoglycemia.

1.3 Rationale for a Systematic Review

According to Kirwan *et al*, (2018), evidence suggests that randomised controlled trials (RCT) and meta-analyses investigated the impact of regular physical activity on Type 2 Diabetes, with the findings being heterogeneous. Available studies differ in the demographics of participants, research-intervention protocol and measured outcome. Considering the variability of material and the constant increase of T2DM, a systematic review is required to:

- Synthesise the currently existing evidence about the influence of physical activity on metabolic health outcomes.
- Compare and discuss different types of physical activity interventions, including aerobic, resistance and combined training.
- Find and identify research gaps to guide future studies.

Several studies are focusing on the immediate effects of physical activity interventions, but just a few publications have actually examined and explained long-term sustainability and impacts on diabetes management and its related complications (Sigal *et al*, 2018). By conducting a systematic review of available literature, this research project will assess if physical activity and exercise benefits can be maintained beyond the period of intervention and if specific modalities will lead to better metabolic adaptation in the longer term.

Another critical aspect that has to be investigated is the effect of generalised physical activity recommendations versus the effect of a personalised exercise plan. Studies are suggesting that planned and tailored exercises based on the person's age, BMI, general fitness level, and any health condition may positively influence metabolic outcome and better management of T2DM (Colberg *et al*, 2016). However, it is not known to what level personalised plan improvement management can be. Most currently existing research, according to Green *et al*, (2024), focuses only on controlled clinical environments, and their application in real life can be challenging and vary from person to person and their adherence to an established plan. Systematic reviews are important in health sciences as they can enhance general evidence-based practice by providing a review of existing literature. The review will be followed by Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA).

1.4 Aim & Objectives

Aim: This systematic review aims to evaluate the impact of structured physical activity on metabolic health outcomes in People with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Objectives

- 1) Examine the effectiveness of resistance, aerobic and combined physical activity interventions on weight loss, insulin sensitivity, HbA1c range test, and cardiovascular health.
- 2) Assess the optimal duration, frequency, and intensity of each exercise intervention for Type 2 Diabetes management.
- 3) Analyse the quality and reliability of currently existing studies by using risk of bias assessment tools.
- 4) Identify barriers and challenges influencing adherence to physical activity interventions in people with T2DM.
- 5) Provide evidence-based recommendations for future studies.

1.5 PICO

According to Schiavenato and Chu (2021), the PICO framework delivers a structured approach to formulating the research question and providing clarity about the focus of the study. By breaking down the research question into smaller components - Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome - this framework helps to establish a range for the systematic review.

- P - Population - Adult who has been diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes.
- I - Intervention - Structured exercising interventions, including resistance, aerobic and combined training.
- C - Comparison - No structured physical activity intervention or standard care.

- O - Outcome - Changes in metabolic health markers - HbA1c test levels, insulin sensitivity, lipid profile, weight management, and fasting blood glucose.

The PICO framework will apply in this systematic review to guide the selection and analysis of studies, making sure that all important and relevant aspects of physical activity and exercise’s impact on T2DM are examined. The findings can contribute to a deeper understanding of effective exercise strategies to manage Diabetes and improve general health outcomes.

2. Methods

2.1 Study Design

This study document adopts a systematic review methodology, which is commonly used to synthesise and review existing research literature and produce an evidence-based summary of the physical activity and its impact on T2DM. The study will adhere to the PRISMA guidelines. Systematic review is an appropriate choice for this secondary research document, as stated by Harris *et al*, (2014), this format allows for a comprehensive assessment of available literature, identifies patterns, consistencies and highlights gaps in existing research. Primarily, the focus is on studies published in peer-reviewed journals that conducted primary or valuable secondary research with data extracted from multiple publication sources, including randomised controlled trials (RCT), cohort studies, and meta-analyses. To ensure quality assessment, the tool AMSTAR 2 will be used to evaluate study reliability (Shea *et al*, 2017).

2.2 Databases

A comprehensive and systematic search of existing literature was conducted by using the following databases and selected based on their relevance to diabetes, physical activity and metabolic health.

Database	Description	Link
PubMed	Focus on biomedical and clinical research, essential for diabetes related studies.	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov

SPORT Discutions	Many publications in relation to sports, physical activity and exercise sciences.	https://www.ebsco.com/products/research-databases/sportdiscus
Cochrane Library	Contain meta-analyses	https://www.cochranelibrary.com
Google Scholar	Used to identify additional literature	https://scholar.google.com
Bielefeld Academic Search Engine (BASE)	An open-access database indexing scholarly research	https://www.base-search.net

According to Baumann (2016), the search strategy should be developed using Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) with appropriate keywords. Carcassi and Sbardolini (2022) stated the use of Boolean operators with the function of truth-value. All have been incorporated into the search to ensure the precision of the research. The graphics below present the keyword search.

(Type 2 Diabetes /OR/ T2D /OR/ Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2)

AND (must include)

(exercise /OR/ physical activity /OR/ aerobic training /OR/ resistance training /OR/ combined training)

AND (must include)

(HbA1c /OR/ glycemic control /OR/ insulin sensitivity /OR/ glucose metabolism /OR/ metabolic health)

The search was completed separately in each database, with keywords being tailored to the specific system of each platform. Initially, the results were checked by title and abstract, and a full document was taken for further evaluation. Duplicate studies were removed. A PRISMA diagram will be created to illustrate the process of search and selection, providing details of the number of studies identified and checked through the included or excluded criteria.

2.3 Eligibility Criteria

According to Ferrari (2015), specific inclusion and exclusion criteria have to be established to enhance relevant high-quality studies included in the research.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Publication is a randomised controlled trial (RCT), a cohort study or a meta-analysis;
- Studies that are published in peer-reviewed journals;
- Research studies focused on the impact of structured physical activity intervention, whether it is aerobic, resistance or combined, on metabolic health outcomes in people affected with Type 2 Diabetes;
- Publications that defined outcome measures, including sensitivity of insulin, HbA1c test level, weight management strategies and lipid profile;
- Studied publications in English and not older than 10 years.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Publications with a focus only on Type 1 Diabetes;
- Research paperwork which does not include physical activity in maintaining Diabetes;
- Research with inadequate quality of methodology - lack of control group, high risk of bias;
- Non-English publications, due to the limitations of their publications.

2.4 Study Selection Process

The selection process was completed systematically to take into consideration the inclusion of high-quality and relevant research studies. The process followed PRISMA principles and, as stated by Tugwell and Tovey (2021), included the following steps:

- 1) All primary and secondary research studies found and used from the database were organised, and the duplicates were removed.
- 2) The titles and abstracts of all found studies were checked to remove those irrelevant to the research topic.
- 3) The full text of potentially relevant publications was checked and assessed to determine their eligibility.
- 4) Evaluation against the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- 5) Studies that met all eligibility criteria were included in the systematic review.
- 6) Provide a PRISMA Flow Diagram for visual transparency.

2.5 Data Extraction

The publication of Mathes *et al*, (2017) suggests that structured data extraction ensures consistency and transparency and provides relevant information, each study being reviewed independently with data extracted and documented. It will be done by using a standardised data extraction form, and key variables will be noted:

- Publication information - author or authors, journal name and year;
- Study design - to classify if it is a journal, systematic review, or article;
- Population characteristics - extract information about sample size, age range, gender and health status;
- Physical activity - what type of intervention is used in a publication, including aerobic, resistance, combined, frequency and duration;
- Outcomes - assessed final results from publication;
- Risk of Bias Assessment - check the quality and reliability of the study by using AMSTAR 2;
- Conclusion and implications - summarised all findings and highlighted their relevance to systematic reviews.

2.6 Quality Assessment

To provide an evaluation of quality and reliability, this systematic review will use A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews (AMSTAR 2). This tool, as stated by Li *et al*, (2022), is designed to assess the methodological quality of systematic reviews, making sure that the research studies included will meet strict standards and do not contain any significant bias and deliver transparency in the selected studies.

Author(s)	Protocol Registered?	Adequate Literature Search?	Appropriate Study Designs Used?	Risk of Bias Assessed?	Appropriate Statistical Methods?	Publication Bias Considered?	Funding Sources Assessed?
Bennetson <i>et al</i> , (2020)	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	P	N
Li <i>et al</i> , (2022)	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

2.7 Data Synthesis

Data received from the publications will be synthesised using a narrative approach. As stated by Lisy and Porritt (2016), narrative synthesis is a method widely used in systematic reviews and allows for the qualitative integration of found material. Melendez-Torres *et al*, (2015) compared the narrative synthetic approach with meta-analysis and reached the conclusion that the second choice may not be proper for research because of huge differences in study designs, used interventions and outcomes.

To compare found material, all studies will be split into groups according to their type of physical activity intervention, including aerobic, resistance, or both, to determine which of those three has the bigger impact on metabolic health outcomes. Each intervention will have its effectiveness assessed by doing a comparison of reported effect sizes, statistical significance and general research conclusions. If a case occurs where findings are highly different or conflicting, further checks will be completed to identify reasons for discrepancies in data, like study populations, used methodologies or adherence level. Kneepkens *et al*, (2019) said that from the chosen studies can be expected heterogeneity in study design, researched interventions and outcome measures and several strategies can be introduced to account for variations. First, conduct a descriptive analysis to summarise the characteristics of the study, including study sample size, intervention type, duration of intervention and main findings. Their methodological quality, as assessed by doing AMSTAR 2, will also be taken into consideration. Selected studies which have been rated as low quality will be interpreted with caution, and any potential impact of those

studies will be discussed in the limitations section. In case of a high number of high quality publications reporting comparable outcomes of their research, a focused analysis will be conducted to strengthen conclusions by using sensitivity analysis.

The presentation of found material will involve multiple formats of presentation to deliver clarity and transparency. A summary table will be presented to organise the characteristics, interventions and important findings of the studies. The narrative description will be used in part to discuss how the results contrast or align with existing literature, providing their context and interpretation. A thematic approach will be used to identify repeating patterns related either to exercises, adherence or long-term metabolic health benefits. According to Lisy and Porritt (2016) structured and systematic synthesis will produce a comprehensive analysis of the impact of physical activity on T2DM management.

3. Results

3.1 Study Characteristics

This systematic review includes various studies investigating the impact of the structural forms of physical activity interventions on metabolic health outcomes in people affected by Type 2 Diabetes. Study selections contained randomised controlled trials and meta-analyses, all published in journals in the last ten years. Selected studies vary in samples, with some studies, like in the journal by Sigal *et al*, (2018), having less than 50 participants, while others conducted the research on much larger populations, like in the cohort study completed by Attanayake *et al*, (2022). The demographic distribution of participants is very diverse, including men and women across different age groups. However, some studies focused on the older population because of the higher prevalence of T2DM (Luo *et al*, 2023).

All interventions assessed in the studies highlight the importance of various exercises: aerobic, resistance, or a combination. Examples of aerobic exercises are listed in the publication of Colberg *et al*, (2016), including walking, jogging, and cycling, which were often prescribed and were prescribed with different intensities ranging from moderate to high. Resistance exercises, physical activity, as stated by Pesta *et al*, (2017), usually involve weight-lifting exercises that target major muscle groups and are performed two or three times a week. Several studies also researched the effect of combined aerobic and resistance training, forming the hypothesis that this approach can bring better metabolic benefits compared to singularity training.

Each physical activity intervention varies and has ranged from short-term studies to those lasting a few weeks, and even months or years. The publication of Luoma *et al*, (2017) contains information on research that lasted from a few weeks to months,

even as long as a few years, with the implementation of exercise programmes to ensure adherence to the program of proper technique for exercises. Other studies aligned with it as well. The frequency of completed exercise sessions generally aligned with recommendations from the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2024).

The primary outcome assessed in selected studies included changes in specific glycemic control markers like HbA1C or insulin sensitivity. Additional secondary outcomes, like inflammatory markers or lipid profiles, are used to determine wider metabolic effects of physical activity intervention. Where most selected studies demonstrated a positive influence of exercise on glycemic control, the level of improvement depended on the type of training, duration, and intensity (Park *et al*, 2022). Some of the research studies additionally examined the adherence level and engagement of participants, implying that long-term adherence to physical activity programs remains a critical factor influencing the sustainability of metabolic benefits.

Selected studies delivered a comprehensive picture of the role of structured physical activity intervention in managing T2DM. The variability in study design, population, age, and training protocol gives an important view on the complexity of exercise prescriptions on population, highlighting the importance of a personalised approach specifically tailored to a person's individual metabolic and lifestyle needs. The following section will further explain the key findings related to glycemic control, overall metabolic health and training program adherence.

3.2 PRISMA Flow Diagram

To make sure that transparency was kept during the study selection process, a PRISMA flow diagram was created. This diagram presents a visualisation of different phases of the study - identification, screening, eligibility assessment, and inclusion in the systematic review. The study selection process started with a search across five selected databases, finding a total number of identified records. After checking for duplicates and removing them, the remaining studies were screened for their suitability based on their title, abstract and study papers that did not meet the established criteria for inclusion were excluded, and the remaining articles were checked with full text review. Additional article exclusion was done after reviewing the full text, mainly because of the methodological limitations, lack of relevant outcomes from research or missing focus on physical activity in publications. The final set of research studies that met the inclusion criteria was used in this systematic review.

3.3 Key Findings

Research studies used in this systematic review have provided substantial evidence that supports the role of physical activity intervention in improving metabolic health outcomes in populations affected by Type 2 Diabetes. One of the most important findings among all studies was the effectiveness of aerobic exercises in reducing HbA1C levels and improving insulin resistance and fasting blood glucose. Multiple randomised controlled trials have demonstrated that moderate to intense levels of aerobic exercise, including walking, cycling, jogging and swimming, were associated with significant reductions in HbA1C (Kanaley *et al*, 2022). Supervised aerobic interventions, as stated in the publication by Kobayashi *et al*, (2023), that last over 12 weeks resulted in greater improvements in glycemic control in comparison with shorter duration training programs.

In addition to aerobic exercises, resistance training is beneficial for the management of Type 2 Diabetes. Various meta-analyses indicated that regular engagement in resistance exercises like weightlifting in the gym, or bodyweight training like callisthenics, led to improved insulin sensitivity and muscle glucose uptake (Bennetsen *et al*, 2020). Publications like the one created by Mukherji *et al*, (2022), focused on the comparison of resistance and aerobic training concluded that resistance-based based often resulted in better body composition with reductions in general fat mass and increased muscle mass. However, the persistent problem was that adherence level in resistance-based training was generally lower than that for aerobic training.

Publications reported that combined aerobic and resistance training was one of the most effective interventions for Type 2 Diabetes management. Research findings indicate that both modalities combined provide additive benefits by improving the metabolism of skeletal muscle and the cardiovascular system (Nery *et ad*, 2017; Sameer Badri AL-Mhanna *et al*, 2024). Research published by Colberg *et al*, (2016) found that participants who were following dual modalities training programs experienced better reduction in HbA1c and improved insulin levels compared with participants engaged in a single exercise form. Trikkalinou *et al*, (2017) stated that combined training is associated with improved functional mobility and quality of life in people with T2DM.

Besides glycemic control, exercise interventions showed a positive impact on lipid profiles, blood pressure regulation and inflammation markers. Regular attendance by the participants in the structural training program led to reductions in LDL cholesterol, triglycerides and systemic inflammation markers like C-reactive protein (Ruze *et al*, 2023). Cardiovascular health was also significantly improved in publications with long-term physical activity adherence, proving how important a sustained level of participation is (Luoma *et al*, 2017; Green *et al*, 2024).

Even when the benefits of physical activity are widely known and well documented, the barriers preventing adherence remain a significant challenge. Studies identified a lack of motivation as the primary reason, followed by physical limitations, fear of hypoglycemia and an insufficient amount of time. Those are common barriers to maintaining regular exercise patterns (Kahlmeier *et al*, 2015; Karami *et al*, 2021). According to Attanayake *et al*, (2022), exercising interventions that incorporate behavioural strategies like goal setting and progress tracking demonstrated a higher success rate in adherence and engagement level. Devices: smartwatches and smartphone applications also helped patients in studies to remain motivated (Whelan *et al*, 2019).

Studies provided strong evidence for the benefit of physical activity, whether it is a singular modality like resistance and aerobic training, or combined, which has an important role to play in managing Type 2 Diabetes. The level of glycemic control improves and depends on exercise intensity, duration and adherence level.

3.4 Quality Assessment

Included studies were assessed for their quality by using the AMSTAR 2 tool and evaluation of multiple methodological aspects like protocol registration, literature search adequacy, risk of bias and statistical methods. The results delivered from it give an overview of the strengths and weaknesses of the selected studies, highlighting differences and variations in methodology. The majority of research studies demonstrated moderate to high quality, particularly in the area of interest.

Conducting comprehensive literature searches and using proper research designs, studies and publications like those completed by Bennetsen *et al*, (2020), Li *et al*, (2022), and Nery *et al*, (2017) presented strong methodological rigour and met the necessary criteria for comprehensive literature search, outcomes, and risk of bias assessment. Those studies have been classified as high quality and provide valuable perspectives about the effectiveness of physical activity on the management of T2DM. Methodological limitations were noted in multiple studies, and one of the most common limitations was a lack of protocol registration in publication studies like those of Mukherji *et al*, (2022) and Molugulu *et al*, (2017). The absence of pre-registered protocols provides an increased risk of selective reporting bias and reduces transparency, ultimately leading to failure of the criteria. Even with limitations part of studies have utilised proper statistical methods to analyse their findings. Publications of Shea *et al*, (2017) and Nery *et al*, (2017) met the criteria in this category, providing further evidence of reliability for the results. Publication bias considerations were addressed in some of the research studies. However, further inconsistencies were found, especially in those studies marked as low and moderate quality. The results from the conducted quality assessment indicate that while most of the studies provide highly valuable contributions, specific

methodological gaps have to be mentioned when interpreting those findings. Studies that marked lower quality scores must be interpreted with caution, especially in those areas where bias risks were not properly mitigated. Given the variability in study quality underscores further need for improved standardisation and methodological transparency in future research studies.

3.5 Summary of Study Outcomes

The general findings from the systematic review indicate that structural physical activity interventions, especially aerobic and resistance training, are important in improving glycemic control and metabolic health in people with Type 2 Diabetes. Across review research studies, aerobic exercise interventions consistently demonstrated evidence in the reduction of HbA1c markers and helped with insulin resistance. The impact of interventions was particularly visible in training programs that were going over 12 weeks, where improvements in glycemic control were much more sustained. Moderate to intense aerobic activities were found to work in the reduction of HbA1c levels by an average of 0,5% to 1% according to publications of Avery *et al*, (2015) and Kanaley *et al*, (2022). Important to note that high-intensity interval training (HIIT) has emerged as an effective alternative, with some studies indicating that short and more intense training sessions can bring similar but often better metabolic benefits when compared with moderate-intensity aerobic (Luo *et al*, 2023).

Training based on resistance interventions showed noticeable metabolic benefits, especially in the area of enhanced insulin sensitivity and muscle glucose uptake. Research studies have indicated that people who are engaged in resistance exercises about two to three times a week have significant improvements in body composition, including a reduction in fat mass and increased lean muscle mass (Pesta *et al*, 2017; Bennetsen *et al*, 2020). Resistance training has been associated with improvements in strength and functional mobility, and those are very important for older people managing their lives with T2DM, as maintaining muscle mass is linked to better glucose regulation inside the body and overall improvements in metabolic function (Mukherji *et al*, 2022). However, comparing those two modalities, the effect of resistance training on glycemic control was variable with factors depending on training intensity, session frequency and participants' adherence.

An important finding in many research publications was that the combined modality of aerobic and resistance training provided more significant improvements in metabolic health. This suggests that by engaging in both exercise modalities can lead towards a greater reduction in HbA1C, improve lipid profiles and positively influence the cardiovascular system if compared with only single modality training (Nery *et al*, 2017; Al-Mhanna *et al*, 2024). Those findings support recommendations from various organisations which are advocating for the integration of multiple

training modalities for optimal diabetes management (Colberg *et al*, 2016). In addition, other published studies like this by Kirwan *et al*, (2018) suggest that exercise frequency is a more important determinant of effectiveness, with structural training programs and adherence over six months can produce greater metabolic benefits.

Wherever benefits of physical activity are outlined, the level of engagement and adherence remained a challenge in many studies and among common challenges were mentioned lack of motivation, time, being afraid of hypoglycemia and having physical limitations (Kahlmeier *et al*, 2015; Karami *et al*, 2021). Research with incorporated behavioural change strategies has demonstrated higher motivation and adherence levels among participants (Attanayake *et al*, 2022; Whelan *et al*, 2019). Additionally, as stated by Luoma *et al*, (2017), physical activity interventions with structured supervision from healthcare professionals showed a higher success rate, highlighting the importance of professional support in managing T2DM.

The next critical observation was the variability in intervention effectiveness based on participants' characteristics. Publications suggest that younger people and those with overall higher fitness levels have responded more favourably to training programs than older generations or individuals with physical limitations. According to the publication of Mukherji *et al*, (2022), personalised physical activity training with adjusted intensity and modality up to the individual's health and preferences was found to have a higher level of engagement and adherence with increased metabolic outcomes. Other research studies are linking cultural and socioeconomic factors to determine the level of adherence and access to fitness facilities. Financial limitations and social perceptions of training vary across different populations (Green *et al*, 2024).

4. Discussion

4.1 Interpretation of Key Findings

The results of this systematic review confirm that structural physical activity has an important role to play in the management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Across gathered and analysed studies, exercises either aerobic, resistance or combined have demonstrated and proved measurable improvements in a person's glycemic control, metabolic health and overall mental and physical well-being. The findings align with previous research, reinforcing further the importance of exercising as a first-line role therapy which can go alongside pharmacological treatments (Colberh *et al*, 2016; Kanaley *et al*, 2022). However, important elements in exercise intervention effectiveness, adherence, and engagement require further evaluation.

One of the most consistent outcomes from research publications was that aerobic training at a high level helped to reduce HbA1c levels, fasting glucose and improve insulin resistance. This finding aligns with research by Avery *et al*, (2015) and Luto *et al*, (2023), which shows that aerobic training with an intensity not lower than moderate but still intense enough can help to get significant metabolic improvements. A program that lasts at least 12 weeks and is planned as long-term was found to be more effective in achieving clinically good level reductions in blood glucose levels. Variability of adherence among participants to the program was a challenge and limiting factor (Attanayake *et al*, 2022; Whelan *et al*, 2019).

Resistance to physical activity interventions has been demonstrated to be beneficial, especially in improving general body composition. The observed increase in lean muscle mass following resistance training has been linked with improved glucose disposal, supported by previous work of Pestal *et al*, (2017) and Bennetsen *et al*, (2020). This format of training, however, showed greater heterogeneity in glycemic outcomes, indicating that things like intensity, frequency and participant characteristics may influence effectiveness. Some studies like this by Mukherji *et al*, (2022) reported a lower adherence rate among participants to follow the training protocol, highlighting how important supervision and behavioural support systems are.

It is worth mentioning that the finding is the training modality of combined training of aerobic and resistance that provides the most substantial metabolic benefits. This aligns with systematic reviews completed by Nery *et al*, (2017) and Al-Mhanna *et al*, (2024), which both concluded that engaging in both aerobic and resistance training brings benefits to glycemic control and supports the cardiovascular system. This combined training approach appears to optimise physiological pathways in multiple ways. According to the World Health Organisation (2024), this is a sufficient approach towards physical activities for people affected by Type 2 Diabetes and recommends doing at least 150 minutes of aerobic exercises with moderate intensity per week, followed by about two or more sessions of resistance training.

The study conducted by Kahlmeier *et al*, (2015) suggests that despite all the benefits that physical activity can bring, adherence to structural training problems remains a challenge, and the biggest one is having a lack of motivation towards training and feeling low due to Diabetes. Karami *et al*, (2021) found that other participants share the fear of hypoglycemia and time limitation. Those are negatively impacting adherence rates. Another publication implemented a strategy of behavioural change strategies like goal setting for participants and digital health tools proved to increase adherence and motivation levels (Attanayake *et al*, 2022; Whelan *et al*, 2019). Having social support or supervised training either with a personal trainer or healthcare professional, as well as using an online coach, also demonstrated increased adherence to the training program (Green *et al*, 2024)

Another important factor with a high level of influence on exercising intervention success was the participants' age and fitness level. Research studies indicated that younger individuals and those with higher fitness levels responded more positively to training programs, while older participants or those with significant mobility impairments faced greater challenges to participation (Mukherji *et al*, 2022). Personalised exercise where each session is adjusted to the person based on age, fitness level and preference (Kirwan *et al*, 2018). Future research should place its focus on developing adaptive exercise protocols that take into account these differences, making sure that participants across all age groups and fitness levels can benefit safely from structural physical activity.

4.2 Comparison with Existing Literature

This systematic review presented findings that align with the hypothesis that physical activity constructed in the structural format is one of the crucial components of Type 2 Diabetes Management. Despite these differences in study methodologies and protocols, exercise interventions and participants exist and contribute to some level of inconsistencies in the literature. This section will explore how the review's findings compare with existing research, highlighting both areas of debate and agreement.

A very strong point of alignment with past studies is the effectiveness of aerobic exercise in improving glycemic control based on the previously completed meta-analyses and systematic reviews (Avery *et al*, 2015; Luo *et al*, 2023). It has been demonstrated that moderate intensity aerobic training influences the reduction of HbA1C levels, fasting glucose and working on insulin resistance. Publication by Luo *et al*, (2023) confirms that sustained training over 12 weeks will bring the biggest metabolic benefits to the body and debates the superiority of high-intensity interval training (HIIT) over continuous training with moderate intensity. However, while HIIT is recognised as a beneficial and promising alternative, more research is needed to assess its long-term sustainability and adherence level in the diabetic population.

In relation to resistance training, findings from this review align with currently existing research that suggests muscle strengthening exercises improve insulin sensitivity and body composition (Pesta *et al*, 2017; Bennetsen *et al*, 2020). However, an inconsistency in the literature is the extent to which resistance exercises alone reduce HbA1C levels. Some research studies support its effectiveness in glycemic control, while others suggest greater variability in outcomes (Mukherji *et al*, 2022). Currently, the review suggests that factors like training intensity, frequency and participant compliance significantly influence the effectiveness of resistance training. Any future study conducted on this topic should focus on a standardised resistance training protocol to improve consistent results.

An important major point in agreement with existing literature is the statement that combining both aerobic and resistance training will provide greater metabolic benefit (Nery *et al*, 2017; Sameer Badri AL-Mhanna *et al*, 2024). This supports existing recommendations from two organisations, the American Diabetes Association (ADA, 2024) and the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2024), which both state that the approach of combined modalities is the best existing strategy to manage T2DM and improve the quality of life for people. Some inconsistencies are present and where studies mentioned before recognising the benefits of combined physical activity concerning Type 2 Diabetes another publication like this by MacDonald *et al*, (2021) says that inconsistencies are remaining in relation to optimal exercise time and intensity and using generally created plan for all individuals will not maximise the benefits of combined training, reinforcing the same need to the creation of personalised exercise prescriptions.

The next important element for discussion in the literature is about barriers and challenges to exercise adherence and behavioural intervention strategies. Based on the studies, the biggest factor is a lack of motivation, followed by fear of hypoglycemia and limited time for long-term participation (Kahlmeier *et al*, 2015; Karami *et al*, 2021). Similar challenges have been reported by the American Diabetes Association (2024), and this highlights the importance of having structural support systems with digital health interventions and, when necessary, behavioural coaching to improve the level of participation (Attanayake *et al*, 2022; Whelan *et al*, 2019). A growing body of research is currently focusing on integrating online coaching systems, wearable technology like new generations of smartwatches and digital applications for smartphones to be incorporated into training programs for people with Type 2 Diabetes (Green *et al*, 2024).

Park *et al*, (2022) research study has suggested that conducting lifestyle-based interventions like limiting sedentary time, walking more often and increasing overall daily movement can offer a complementary set of benefits and can be completed alongside an exercise program. While the structural form of exercising is highly effective, study also indicates that small but frequent movement breaks throughout the day may contribute to better glucose control and reduced levels of insulin resistance. This shows potential in integrating structured training with a lifestyle change approach to maximise health benefits. The publication of Sigal *et al*, (2022) focused on the role of psychological and behavioural factors in exercise adherence. Those gained attention in diabetes research and studies indicate that motivation, self-efficacy and perceived exercise benefits are strongly influenced and participation in physical activity training programs, suggesting that behavioural interventions, group-based support programs and cognitive behavioural therapy can benefit the person.

4.3 Practical and Clinical Implications

Demonstrated findings in this systematic review have practical and clinical implications for many professions, including healthcare, policymakers, and people affected by Type 2 Diabetes. By implementing structural physical activity training programs for diabetes care, patients have the chance to benefit from many factors to improve the overall quality of their lives. However, to ensure an effective transition from the publication into a real-life setting, it requires addressing various barriers to exercise participation, optimising physical activity intervention strategies and integrating exercise into a daily routine (Baltac & Dawidowicz, 2025).

Given the existence of strong evidence that supports structural physical activity as one of the main interventions for T2DM, it can be integrated into clinical practice, and healthcare professionals can provide exercise prescriptions for patients. The American Diabetes Association (2019) recommends that a person affected by Type 2 Diabetes should do at least 150 minutes per week of aerobic exercises with moderate intensity, with the addition of resistance training two or three times a week. General Practitioners, as stated by Stuij (2018), should be able to collaborate with physiotherapists, exercise physiologists and certified fitness professionals to make sure patients are receiving personalised guidance on effective physical activity.

Policymakers have to prioritise public health initiatives that can promote physical activity. The World Health Organisation (2024) advocates for the creation of various programs on the community level that can provide accessible and affordable opportunities for exercising. According to Brown *et al*, (2018), workplace wellness programs and their related interventions may bring benefits to individuals with T2DM. The authors stated that the intervention was conducted on a group of fewer than 20 employees, with an hour-long session per week held during lunch break. Outcomes measured over 6 or 12 months delivered positive outcomes with benefits to the health of an employee.

Implications of physical activity are also coming because of the development of digital health interventions, and as mentioned before, smartwatches, online coaching or smartphone apps are just a small fraction of it. Nguyen *et al*, (2024) mentioned that further development of this type of intervention can support education, prevention and management of Diabetes by providing knowledge about the disease, creating support groups and overcoming challenges associated with traditional self-management education. Azelton *et al*, (2021) said that personalised online coaching has much potential to improve clinical outcomes through lifestyle and behavioural approaches like motivational interviewing and goal setting.

Patient education and awareness are the key factors in managing T2DM, and many people do not fully understand the role of physical activity and exercise in managing

their condition (Kahlmeier *et al*, 2015; Karami *et al*, 2021). One of the major challenges in keeping up with exercising is complications in individuals with Diabetes - neuropathy, joint pain, cardiovascular disease - which make traditional training programs being difficult to follow. Colberg *et al*, (2016) said that adaptive training programs like low-impact aerobic activities, aquatic therapies or chair-based resistance training may provide alternatives and make training more accessible. Another factor influencing is psychological and mental well-being, and Abbas *et al*, (2023) said that depression, anxiety and low self-esteem are common among people with diabetes, often reducing motivation to engage in physical activity. Sigal *et al*, (2018) stated that any behavioural technique or strategy may help individuals to adjust their perspective and improve mental well-being. Introducing mental health support alongside exercise interventions can lead to improved engagement in training programs. Scavarda *et al*, (2021) mentioned that environmental and social factors that may influence adherence with limited access to exercise are financial struggles, which are commonly stated reasons for low participation levels. Implementation of community exercise programmes with free entry and offering financial incentives or discounts for gym membership or classes can encourage overcoming those challenges. Additionally, the creation of a support group for people affected by Diabetes can help improve the well-being of an individual (Lidegaard *et al*, 2016).

4.4 Strengths of the Study

This systematic review has several noticeable strengths that enhance the general value, validity and applicability of the findings used. The first strong side is the systematic and structured methodology, which follows PRISMA guidelines to have transparency and reproducibility (Sarkis-Onofre *et al*, 2021). The use of multiple databases, including PubMed, Google Scholar, and Bielefeld Academic Search Engine, with strictly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria, tried to minimise the selection bias and improve the comprehensiveness of the literature. AMSTAR-2 was also used to critically assess the quality of selected research studies, making sure that methodological weaknesses were identified and accounted for in result interpretation (Lu *et al*, 2020). The second major strong side of this study is a detailed comprehensive evaluation of different exercise modalities - aerobic, resistance and combined training - By conducting a comparison of those modalities with their effectiveness, it provides an understanding of how structured physical activity can be adjusted for a person with Type 2 Diabetes (Magalhães *et al*, 2018). This comparison approach allows for more flexibility and personalised exercise plan recommendations. The incorporation of a multidimensional perspective on physical activity adherence level and behavioural interventions is often overlooked in traditional exercise-focused research. By recognising that adherence to the program remains a massive challenge for participants, this study evaluated sources of

motivation, digital health solutions and existing psychological barriers that may influence engagement levels in structural physical activity programs (Sigal *et al*, 2018). Taking into consideration various factors like access to resources and participants' motivation, this systematic review contributes to physiological evaluation but additionally to a more holistic understanding of long-term intervention success (Ispas *et al*, 2025). The next strong side is reviewing the findings with clinical and public health relevance. Those findings can directly provide necessary information about exercise prescriptions and, to some extent, support the development of public health policies. Additionally, it can guide community-based exercise program interventions (WHO, 2024). It discussed and acknowledged the existing need for scalable, accessible and adaptable exercise programs to reach a much diverse population. The recent inclusion of studies from 2015 to 2025 ensures that all data used in this review is of value and delivers up-to-date evidence in the field of physical activity and metabolic health.

4.5 Theoretical and Conceptual Implications

Findings in this systematic review provide empirical evidence of structural physical activity plans on metabolic benefits for people affected by the disease. It further reinforces and extends several theoretical frameworks important and relevant to chronic disease management and influences behavioural change.

The review outcomes align with the biopsychosocial model, and Wade and Halligan (2017) explain that this posits biological, psychological and social factors collectively can influence health outcomes. Findings from the studies support this by showing that physiological benefits - improvement of glycemic control with insulin sensitivity are often related to psychological and social elements (Sigal *et al*, 2018). This broad understanding of care for people with diabetes should not be seen only as a biological intervention but as a behavioural and social experience. Phillips and Guarnaccia (2017) state the relevance of the Self-Determination Theory in adherence promotion toward physical activity. This theory highlights the importance of intrinsic motivation, autonomy, competence and relation in sustaining long-term behavioural change. Several mechanisms like peer support, goal setting or using online support coaching are aligned with principles of theory and using them in practice may bring additional benefits in diabetes management. Further is the Health Belief Model, which, according to Shabibi *et al*, (2017) gives particular perspectives on why some people would engage in exercising where others would not. Various constructs like perceived susceptibility, perceived benefits and barriers, self-efficacy are central to this Model. An example here, fear of having hypoglycemia and low fitness level are seen as barriers, whereas goals of weight loss, improving glucose reading in the body and having increased energy level are seen as motivation, and a person is more likely to continue participating in the program.

At the population level, the World Health Organisation (2018) and its Global Action Plan on Physical Activity for the years 2018-2030 advocate for increased physical activity to reduce non-communicable diseases. WHO's policy direction and recommendations of 150 minutes of moderate training intensity with muscle strengthening activities are general and easily adaptable guidelines.

5 Limitations of the Study

One of the primary limitations of this review is the potential for selection bias during the inclusion process. Despite the completion of extensive searches in the databases, some of the studies could have been missed due to language restrictions, database limitations, or unpublished research. As stated by Mlinarić *et al*, (2017), publication bias is a real issue as studies that demonstrate positive value are more likely to be published than those reporting negative results. The exclusion of non-English studies and unpublished studies could lead to an overestimation of exercise benefits in glycemic control and metabolic health processes. A key issue is inherent bias during the study selection, which may occur because of huge variations in study design, population sample or even intervention protocols. Cook and Therrien (2017) said that studies with shorter follow-up periods or having small sample sizes can be overrepresented in the available literature, creating an imbalance in the weight of evidence. Another important point is that research sponsored by the industry often has a specific interest in reporting favourable outcomes, which may skew data towards exercise interventions with positive impact (Mukherji *et al*, 2022).

A used search strategy could result in missing relevant data, and while multiple databases have been used to conduct the search, some high-impact journals or any grey literature may not have been fully represented. Nery *et al*, (2017) said that each database has differences in indexing practices, variations in terminology and additionally, inconsistent reporting procedures of exercise interventions in research publications may lead to situations of exclusion of potentially relevant studies. Another challenge faced in this systematic review was heterogeneity in inclusion and exclusion criteria across selected publications. Some conducted trials included only highly motivated participants or people with good fitness levels, leading to situations of potentially biased results towards more favourable exercise outcomes. According to Atkinson and Cipriani (2018), this may raise concerns regarding its application in the real world as individuals with limited physical activity experience or mobility impairments can respond differently to training programs. Some of the data in publications have been self-reported by participants, which can create over- or under-reporting, leading ultimately to bias and affecting accuracy in assessing the level of engagement and adherence. Khare and Vedel (2019) mentioned that using objective measures like glucose monitoring or supervised exercises can help in mitigation, as it will provide more reliable and quantifiable data.

The AMSTAR-2 tool has been used for methodological quality assessment, despite many studies being rated as moderate or low quality, mainly because of issues like having a small sample size, lacking randomisation and inadequate blinding (Shea *et al*, 2017). This absence of a control group in some trials and reliance on the mentioned self-reporting could introduce measurement bias, affecting the reliability of findings. A critical limitation across studies was inconsistency in reporting adherence levels to exercise interventions. The publication of Marrella (2023) stated that adherence has an important role in determining the long-term effectiveness of structural physical activity. However, many studies relied on self-reported data or did not report any. This gap makes it challenging to properly assess whether improvements in metabolic health came directly from exercise interventions or it was influenced by participant engagement level.

Another challenge was the issue of generalisability. Part of the studies conducted their research on diverse populations with varying demographics, health conditions and socioeconomic backgrounds, as stated by Hurland and Houston (2020), may raise questions about which results can be universally applied. Many publications focused on conducting research in highly controlled environments where participants engaged in structured and supervised exercise programs. This helped to maintain intervention correctness and adherence level, but does not reflect real-world scenarios where participants can face financial, logistical and motivational barriers. The next factor limiting generalisation is the exclusion of specific subpopulations from many of the review publications. For example, a systematic review by Goff *et al*, (2021) found significant ethnic differences in lifestyle interventions on T2DM and related outcomes. This publication suggested that while lifestyle choices and interventions reduce diabetes risk in populations, the degree of their effectiveness depends on ethnicity, with some groups experiencing greater effects in glycemic control than others. Variability in exercise protocols affects the applicability of findings to the broader population. Some research studies conducted research with HIIT regimens, while others were based either on low or moderate intensity programs. Differences in session frequency, duration and professional steps further complicate the development of universal exercise guidelines for Type 2 Diabetes.

6. Recommendations

6.1 Clinical Practice

According to the publication of Kime *et al*, (2020), healthcare professionals should more actively incorporate structures of physical activity into routine diabetes management. This means not only advising patients to be more active but also delivering detailed training plans with adjustments based on a person's health, preferences and capabilities. Many different health professions would need to cooperate, including general practitioners, endocrinologists, physiotherapists and

certified fitness professionals to create tailored and safe programs. Warburton *et al*, (2021) suggest conducting routine assessments, a screening tool like the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire can be used and guide the thought process of customisation of intervention and ensure the safety of the patient, especially for those who are affected by mobility limitations. Clinicians who are going to create and tailor training plans as stated by Shah *et al*, (2021) should be trainers in exercise counselling techniques and understand the role of physical activity in glycemic control with cardiovascular risk reduction. The mental well-being of a person is taken into consideration as well. Integration of intervention models to routine GP consultations can help in the process of behavioural change, and referral systems to supervised training programs can influence a person's long-term adherence level. Documenting physical activity levels during GP consultation in the same way as blood or BMI is registered can reinforce its importance in diabetes management.

6.2 Public Health and Policy

Publication by Dempsey *et al*, (2021) suggests that various governments and public health agencies should increase their financial investments in physical activity programs among local communities with a focus on people affected by T2DM. Different initiatives like free fitness classes, exercise referral schemes, and green space development can contribute to the creation of an environment that encourages people to have active lifestyles. Healthcare policies should prioritise the promotion of physical activity as a primary strategy for prevention (Kraus *et al*, 2015). Incentive-based approaches like gym discounts or substitution for group activities may improve engagement and adherence levels, particularly among socioeconomically disadvantaged groups. In addition to this, governmental policies should promote intersectoral collaboration that would involve healthcare providers, education institutions, workplaces and urban planners (Whitsel *et al*, 2023). The creation of environments that facilitate exercising across all ages, with further integration of physical activity into national diabetes strategies, will create the need for sustainable long-term investment in prevention care.

6.3 Digital Health Integration

Further introduction of digital tools in diabetes care with various technologies like wearable fitness trackers, mobile health apps and online coaching should be encouraged. Those technologies demonstrated usefulness in the promotion of engagement and adherence levels. National healthcare systems and their private equivalents invest in the development of digital platforms that deliver real-time feedback, sensing personalised reminders about exercising and tracking the progress (Shah and Garg, 2015). Patients should be educated and properly supported in using digital technologies effectively. Integration of those systems additionally prioritises data privacy, user friendliness and inclusivity.

Viswanadham (2021) mentioned that it is not just healthcare providers but tech developers and academic institutions that may collaborate and create evidence-based digital interventions adjusted to the needs of persons with Type 2 Diabetes. Artificial Intelligence and machine learning algorithms can enhance personalisation even more by learning about the behavioural patterns of a user and later adapting recommendations accordingly to a person's needs. Long-term integration of digital technologies into national health systems and their providers can increase their adoption, sustainability and further development. As the technology of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning becomes more central in healthcare, ensuring equitable access for everyone will be important (Abhari *et al*, 2019).

6.4. Education and Patient Empowerment

Gómez-Velasco *et al*, (2019) mentioned that education among people is essential in ensuring long-term adherence to training programs, and patients have to understand not only the physiological benefits of exercising but also how to manage various barriers and challenges, including fear of injury or hypoglycemia. Structured education sessions about diabetes should introduce physical activity modules that explain different behavioural strategies like goal setting, problem-solving skills and motivational interviewing. Cheng *et al*, (2018) suggest that all healthcare providers should foster a culture of empowerment and encourage making shared decisions and help build confidence in patients. Psychological support in sessions like cognitive behavioural therapy and group-based coaching can be introduced where appropriate. Education resources should be available to patients in many languages and formats to accommodate the learning and literacy levels of many diverse groups. Various tools like infographics, smartphone apps and videos can influence patient engagement levels and knowledge retention. The creation of workshops is another key factor which can positively influence and foster a sense of community among the patients (Dickinson *et al*, 2017). Patient empowerment with Type 2 Diabetes relies on creating an accessible and supportive care environment for everyone.

6.5 Equity and Accessibility

Hasson *et al*, (2017) suggest that in order to ensure equitable access for everyone to the benefits of physical activity, training programs have to be designed with diversity and inclusion in mind. This includes addressing disparities in the geography by expanding services to the rural areas and offering low-cost or free activity options. Program adaptations for individuals with physical or cognitive impairments should be offered. Health strategies additionally should seek ways to reduce social stigma and promote exercising as a positive experience for people of all backgrounds and abilities.

7. Conclusion

This systematic review, based on secondary research, demonstrated that structural physical activity, whether aerobic, resistance or a combination of both modalities, plays an important role in improving metabolic and overall health outcomes in people living with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Across gathered and analysed literature, consistent evidence supported having a positive impact of exercising on improved glycemic control, better insulin sensitivity, overall body composition and cardiovascular system. The most effective training programs usually include supervised interventions completed over a longer period that encourage adherence and engagement by using various behavioural strategies connected with personalised planning, and, where possible, digital support.

Two combined exercise modalities - aerobic and resistance - have proven to be the most effective strategy, demonstrating higher improvements than either aerobic or resistance training alone. These findings are important and support currently existing guidelines and health recommendations, advocating and promoting for integration of physical activity into standard care programs for people with Type 2 Diabetes. However, sometimes, the adherence level in the studies remained at a critically low level and presented a challenge. Different psychological, social, and environmental barriers were limiting consistent participation, giving suggestions for a more adaptable and inclusive intervention.

The importance of behavioural change strategies and digital technologies to improve adherence among participants and sustain their long-term engagement was discussed by introducing smartphone health apps, online coaching and smartwatches to offer feedback in real time with accountability, which is particularly important in programs designed to be completed at home or self-supervised. The involvement of healthcare professionals is necessary to support patients' motivation by educating and encouraging them. Data shows it improves confidence and influences participation rates.

The diversity of the patient population affected by T2DM should be considered. Age, overall fitness level, socioeconomic status and cultural background mean that one standard approach is not sustainable for everyone. The review underlined the importance of personalised interventions, where a type of exercise, its frequency, intensity and delivery mode are adjusted to a person's needs. As an example, older generations or people with mobility issues may benefit more from low-impact exercises and resistance-based interventions, supported by supervision and adaptive strategies. In comparison, younger, more active individuals can respond better to higher intensity aerobic or combined intervention programs with some level of autonomy.

Physical activity's role in improving mental well-being, quality of life and helping in stress reduction is often underestimated. Many people who are living with T2DM experience daily psychological challenges and, with time, develop anxiety, depression or diabetes distress, which can interfere with training program engagement. Exercise programs, when structured, should include social engagement, a degree of behavioural support and daily progress tracking, as this can play a critical role in addressing these problems.

From a public health perspective, findings reinforce the importance of community inclusion strategies to promote and foster a respectful and safe environment for physical activity. This includes not only building a support circle and offering free or discounted training opportunities but also ensuring that national law and policies will prioritise physical activity and important prevention and management tools in case of chronic diseases. By increasing awareness through various public campaigns, empowering patients and leveraging available digital solutions, everyone can contribute to a safer and more inclusive model of care.

The essential thing is to acknowledge that the healthcare field is evolving, and future interventions have to be adaptive and cost-efficient. As health systems around the world face constantly rising demand, the integration of exercise programs into a care routine offers a proactive way and a preventive approach that can lead to a reduction of long-term costs related to healthcare and improve benefits for patients' health. Integration of physical activity into national health guidelines, electronic health records, and prioritisation of exercise counselling may create many opportunities for implementation.

This systematic review provided the answer that structured physical activity should be considered as a key element in Type 2 Diabetes Management, and not just as supplementation, but as a core competency of a multidisciplinary treatment strategy. The provided evidence is clear, physical activity is effective and transforming the management and lived experience of those affected by type 2 Diabetes. Successful implementation depends heavily on.

References

- Abbas, Q., Latif, S., Ayaz Habib, H., Shahzad, S., Sarwar, U., Shahzadi, M., Ramzan, Z. and Washdev, W. (2023). Cognitive behavior therapy for diabetes distress, depression, health anxiety, quality of life and treatment adherence among patients with type-II diabetes mellitus: a randomized control trial. *BMC Psychiatry*, 23(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-023-04546-w>.
- Abhari, S., Niakan Kalhori, S.R., Ebrahimi, M., Hasannejadasl, H. and Garavand, A. (2019). Artificial Intelligence Applications in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Care: Focus on Machine Learning Methods. *Healthcare Informatics Research*, 25(4), p.248. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4258/hir.2019.25.4.248>.
- A. B. Attanayake, H.M.D., Barnett, A., Burton, N.W., Brown, W.J. and Cramb, S.M. (2022). Diabetes and physical activity: A prospective cohort study. *PLOS ONE*, 17(10), p.e0276761. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0276761>.
- ADA (2024). *It's a great time to get moving.* | ADA. [online] diabetes.org. Available at: <https://diabetes.org/health-wellness/fitness>.
- American Diabetes Association (2019). 5. lifestyle management: Standards of medical care in diabetes—2019. *Diabetes Care*, 42(Supplement 1), pp.S46–S60. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2337/dc19-s005>.
- Atkinson, L.Z. and Cipriani, A. (2018). How to Carry out a Literature Search for a Systematic Review: a Practical Guide. *BJPsych Advances*, 24(2), pp.74–82. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1192/bja.2017.3>.
- Avery, L., Flynn, D., Dombrowski, S.U., van Wersch, A., Sniehotta, F.F. and Trenell, M.I. (2015). Successful behavioural strategies to increase physical activity and improve glucose control in adults with Type 2 diabetes. *Diabetic Medicine*, 32(8), pp.1058–1062. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/dme.12738>.
- Azelton, K.R., Crowley, A.P., Vence, N., Underwood, K., Morris, G., Kelly, J. and Landry, M.J. (2021). Digital Health Coaching for Type 2 Diabetes: Randomized Controlled Trial of Healthy at Home. *Frontiers in Digital Health*, 3. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2021.764735>.
- Baumann, N. (2016). How to Use the Medical Subject Headings (MeSH). *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 70(2), pp.171–174. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcp.12767>.
- Bennetsen, S.L., Feineis, C.S., Legaard, G.E., Lyngbæk, M.P.P., Karstoft, K. and Ried-Larsen, M. (2020). The Impact of Physical Activity on Glycemic Variability Assessed by Continuous Glucose Monitoring in Patients With Type 2 Diabetes

Mellitus: A Systematic Review. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, 11.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2020.00486>.

Baltac, A. and Dawidowicz, A. (2025) 'Mental Health Changes During Fitness Training: A Narrative Review of Psychological Stages, Challenges and Coping Strategies'. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15380963.

Brown, S.A., García, A.A., Zuñiga, J.A. and Lewis, K.A. (2018). Effectiveness of workplace diabetes prevention programs: A systematic review of the evidence. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 101(6), pp.1036–1050.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2018.01.001>.

Carcassi, F. and Sbardolini, G. (2022). Assertion, denial, and the evolution of Boolean operators. *Mind & Language*, 38(5). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/mila.12448>.

Cheng, L., Sit, J.W.H., Choi, K., Chair, S., Li, X., Wu, Y., Long, J. and Tao, M. (2018). Effectiveness of a patient-centred, empowerment-based intervention programme among patients with poorly controlled type 2 diabetes: A randomised controlled trial. *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 79, pp.43–51.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2017.10.021>.

Colberg, S.R., Sigal, R.J., Yardley, J.E., Riddell, M.C., Dunstan, D.W., Dempsey, P.C., Horton, E.S., Castorino, K. and Tate, D.F. (2016). Physical activity/exercise and diabetes: A position statement of the american diabetes association. *Diabetes Care*, [online] 39(11), pp.2065–2079. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2337/dc16-1728>.

Cook, B.G. and Therrien, W.J. (2017). Null Effects and Publication Bias in Special Education Research. *Behavioral Disorders*, 42(4), pp.149–158.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0198742917709473>.

Dempsey, P.C., Friedenreich, C.M., Leitzmann, M.F., Buman, M.P., Lambert, E., Willumsen, J. and Bull, F. (2021). Global Public Health Guidelines on Physical Activity and Sedentary Behavior for People Living With Chronic Conditions: A Call to Action. *Journal of Physical Activity and Health*, 18(1), pp.76–85.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1123/jpah.2020-0525>.

Dickinson, J.K., Guzman, S.J., Maryniuk, M.D., O'Brian, C.A., Kadohiro, J.K., Jackson, R.A., D'Hondt, N., Montgomery, B., Close, K.L. and Funnell, M.M. (2017). The Use of Language in Diabetes Care and Education. *The Diabetes Educator*, 43(6), pp.551–564. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0145721717735535>.

Ferrari, R. (2015). Writing narrative style literature reviews. *Medical Writing*, 24(4), pp.230–235. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1179/2047480615Z.000000000329>.

Green, J.B., Crowley, M.J., Sathish Thirunavukkarasu, Maruthur, N.M. and Oldenburg, B. (2024). The Final Frontier in Diabetes Care: Implementing Research in Real-World Practice. *Diabetes Care*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2337/dci24-0001>.

HASSON, R.E., BROWN, D.R., DORN, J., BARKLEY, L., TORGAN, C., WHITT-GLOVER, M., AINSWORTH, B. and KEITH, N. (2017). Achieving Equity in Physical Activity Participation. *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 49(4), pp.848–858. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0000000000001161>.

Harris, J.D., Quatman, C.E., Manring, M.M., Siston, R.A. and Flanigan, D.C. (2014). How to write a systematic review. *The American journal of sports medicine*, 42(11), pp.2761–8. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0363546513497567>.

Hulland, J. and Houston, M.B. (2020). Why systematic review papers and meta-analyses matter: an introduction to the special issue on generalizations in marketing. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 48(3), pp.351–359. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-020-00721-7>.

International Diabetes Federation (2024). *Diabetes Facts & figures*. [online] International Diabetes Federation. Available at: <https://idf.org/about-diabetes/diabetes-facts-figures/>

Ispas, S., Nelson Twakor, A., Mindrescu, N.M., Ispas, V., Tofolean, D.E., Mercore Hutanu, E., Petcu, A., Deacu, S., Iordache, I.E., Bica, C.I., Petcu, L.C., Gherghiceanu, F., Popoviciu, M.S. and Pantea Stoian, A. (2025). From Sedentary to Success: How Physical Activity Transforms Diabetes Management: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Mind and Medical Sciences*, 12(1), p.10. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/jmms12010010>.

Kahlmeier, S., Wijnhoven, T.M.A., Alpiger, P., Schweizer, C., Breda, J. and Martin, B.W. (2015). National physical activity recommendations: systematic overview and analysis of the situation in European countries. *BMC Public Health*, [online] 15(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-015-1412-3>.

Karami, H., Shirvani Shiri, M., Rezapour, A., Sarvari Mehrabadi, R. and Afshari, S. (2021). The association between diabetic complications and health-related quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes: a cross-sectional study from Iran. *Quality of Life Research*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-021-02792-7>.

Kanaley, J.A., Colberg, S.R., Corcoran, M.H., Malin, S.K., Rodriguez, N.R., Crespo, C.J., Kirwan, J.P. and Zierath, J.R. (2022). Exercise/physical activity in individuals with type 2 diabetes: A consensus statement from the American College of Sports Medicine. *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, [online] 54(2), pp.353–368. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0000000000002800>.

Khare, S.R. and Vedel, I. (2019). Recall bias and reduction measures: an example in primary health care service utilization. *Family Practice*, 36(5), pp.672–676. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmz042>.

Kime, N., Pringle, A., Zwolinsky, S. and Vishnubala, D. (2020). How prepared are healthcare professionals for delivering physical activity guidance to those with diabetes? A formative evaluation. *BMC Health Services Research*, 20(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-4852-0>.

Kneepkens, E.-L., Brouwers, C., Singotani, R.G., de Bruijne, M.C. and Karapinar-Çarkit, F. (2019). How do studies assess the preventability of readmissions? A systematic review with narrative synthesis. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 19(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0766-0>.

Kraus, W.E., Bittner, V., Appel, L., Blair, S.N., Church, T., Després, J.-P., Franklin, B.A., Miller, T.D., Pate, R.R., Taylor-Piliae, R.E., Vafiadis, D.K. and Whitsel, L. (2015). The National Physical Activity Plan: A Call to Action From the American Heart Association. *Circulation*, 131(21), pp.1932–1940. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1161/cir.0000000000000203>.

Lidegaard, L.P., Schwennesen, N., Willaing, I. and Faerch, K. (2016). Barriers to and motivators for physical activity among people with Type 2 diabetes: patients' perspectives. *Diabetic Medicine*, 33(12), pp.1677–1685. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/dme.13167>.

Lin, C.-Y., Cheung, M.K.T., Hung, A.T.F., Poon, P.K.K., Chan, S.C.C. and Chan, C.C.H. (2020). Can a modified theory of planned behavior explain the effects of empowerment education for people with type 2 diabetes? *Therapeutic Advances in Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 11, p.204201881989752. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/2042018819897522>.

Li, L., Asemota, I., Liu, B., Gomez-Valencia, J., Lin, L., Arif, A.W., Siddiqi, T.J. and Usman, M.S. (2022). AMSTAR 2 appraisal of systematic reviews and meta-analyses in the field of heart failure from high-impact journals. *Systematic Reviews*, 11(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-022-02029-9>.

Lisy, K. and Porritt, K. (2016). Narrative Synthesis. *International Journal of Evidence-Based Healthcare*, 14(4), p.201. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1097/01.xeb.0000511348.97198.8c>.

Lu, C., Lu, T., Ge, L., Yang, N., Yan, P. and Yang, K. (2020). Use of AMSTAR-2 in the methodological assessment of systematic reviews: protocol for a methodological study. *Annals of Translational Medicine*, [online] 8(10). doi:<https://doi.org/10.21037/atm-20-392a>.

Luo, M., Yu, C., Pozo, D., Chen, L. and Ding, D. (2023). Accelerometer-measured intensity-specific physical activity, genetic risk and incident type 2 diabetes: a prospective cohort study. *p.bjsports-106653*.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2022-106653>.

Luoma, K.A., Leavitt, I.M., Marrs, J.C., Nederveld, A.L., Regensteiner, J.G., Dunn, A.L., Glasgow, R.E. and Huebschmann, A.G. (2017). How can clinical practices pragmatically increase physical activity for patients with type 2 diabetes? A systematic review. *Translational Behavioral Medicine*, 7(4), pp.751–772.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13142-017-0502-4>.

Kirwan, J.P., Sacks, J. and Nieuwoudt, S. (2018). The Essential Role of Exercise in the Management of Type 2 Diabetes. *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine*, 84(7), pp.15–21. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.84.s1.03>.

Kobayashi, Y., Long, J., Dan, S., Johannsen, N.M., Talamoa, R., Sonia Sunita Raghuram, Chung, S., Kent, K., Basina, M., Lamendola, C., Haddad, F., Leonard, M.B., Church, T.S. and Palaniappan, L. (2023). Strength training is more effective than aerobic exercise for improving glycaemic control and body composition in people with normal-weight type 2 diabetes: A randomised controlled trial. *Diabetologia*, 66(10), pp.1897–1907.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00125-023-05958-9>.

Low, C.Y., Gan, W.L., Lai, S.J., Tam, R.S.-M., Tan, J.F., Dietl, S., Chuah, L.H., Voelcker, N. and Bakhtiar, A. (2025). Critical updates on oral insulin drug delivery systems for type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of nanobiotechnology*, [online] 23(1), p.16. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-024-03062-7>.

MacDonald, C.S., Ried-Larsen, M., Soleimani, J., Alsawas, M., Lieberman, D.E., Ismail, A.S., Serafim, L.P., Yang, T., Prokop, L., Joyner, M., Murad, M.H. and Barwise, A. (2021). A systematic review of adherence to physical activity interventions in individuals with type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, [online] 37(8), p.e3444. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/dmrr.3444>.

Magalhães, J.P., Júdice, P.B., Ribeiro, R., Andrade, R., Raposo, J., Dores, H., Bicho, M. and Sardinha, L.B. (2018). Effectiveness of high-intensity interval training combined with resistance training versus continuous moderate-intensity training combined with resistance training in patients with type 2 diabetes: A one-year randomized controlled trial. *Diabetes, Obesity and Metabolism*, 21(3), pp.550–559. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/dom.13551>.

Marrella, G. (2023). Exploring Women's Psychological and Emotional Experiences in Long-Term Strength Training Adherence. *American Journal of Health Education*, pp.1–15. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/19325037.2023.2277934>.

Mathes, T., Klößen, P. and Pieper, D. (2017). Frequency of Data Extraction Errors and Methods to Increase Data Extraction quality: a Methodological Review. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 17(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-017-0431-4>.

Melendez-Torres, G.J., Thomas, J., Richardson, M., Felix, L., Lorenc, T., Thomas, S. and Petticrew, M. (2015). Lessons from comparing narrative synthesis and meta-analysis in a systematic review. *The Lancet*, 386, p.S9. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(15\)00847-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(15)00847-8).

Mlinarić, A., Horvat, M. and Šupak Smolčić, V. (2017). Dealing with the positive publication bias: Why you should really publish your negative results. *Biochemia Medica*, 27(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.11613/bm.2017.030201>.

Molugulu, N., Yee, L.S., Ye, Y.T., Khee, T.C., Nie, L.Z., Yee, N.J., Yee, T.K., Liang, T.C. and Kesharwani, P. (2017). Systematic review of metformin monotherapy and dual therapy with sodium glucose co-transporter 2 inhibitor (SGLT-2) in treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Research and Clinical Practice*, 132, pp.157–168. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diabres.2017.07.025>.

Mukherji, A.B., Lu, D., Qin, F., Hedlin, H., Johannsen, N.M., Chung, S., Kobayashi, Y., Haddad, F., Lamendola, C., Basina, M., Talamoa, R., Myers, J. and Palaniappan, L. (2022). Effectiveness of a Community-Based Structured Physical Activity Program for Adults With Type 2 Diabetes. *JAMA Network Open*, [online] 5(12), p.e2247858. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.47858>.

Nery, C., Moraes, S.R.A.D., Novaes, K.A., Bezerra, M.A., Silveira, P.V.D.C. and Lemos, A. (2017). Effectiveness of resistance exercise compared to aerobic exercise without insulin therapy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus: a meta-analysis. *Brazilian Journal of Physical Therapy*, [online] 21(6), pp.400–415. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjpt.2017.06.004>.

Nguyen, V., Ara, P., Simmons, D. and Osuagwu, U.L. (2024). The Role of Digital Health Technology Interventions in the Prevention of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Systematic Review. *Clinical Medicine Insights. Endocrinology and Diabetes*, 17, p.11795514241246419. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/11795514241246419>.

Park, S.H., Yao, J., Chua, X.H., Chandran, S.R., Gardner, D.S.L., Khoo, C.M., Müller-Riemenschneider, F., Whitton, C. and van Dam, R.M. (2022). Diet and Physical Activity as Determinants of Continuously Measured Glucose Levels in Persons at High Risk of Type 2 Diabetes. *Nutrients*, [online] 14(2), p.366. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14020366>.

Pesta, D.H., Goncalves, R.L.S., Madiraju, A.K., Strasser, B. and Sparks, L.M. (2017). Resistance training to improve type 2 diabetes: working toward a prescription for the future. *Nutrition & Metabolism*, 14(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12986-017-0173-7>.

Phillips, A.S. and Guarnaccia, C.A. (2017). Self-determination theory and motivational interviewing interventions for type 2 diabetes prevention and treatment: A systematic review. *Journal of Health Psychology*, 25(1), p.135910531773760. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/1359105317737606>.

Ruze, R., Liu, T., Zou, X., Song, J., Chen, Y., Xu, R., Yin, X. and Xu, Q. (2023). Obesity and type 2 diabetes mellitus: connections in epidemiology, pathogenesis, and treatments. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, [online] 14(1161521). doi:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2023.1161521>.

Sameer Badri AL-Mhanna, Alexios Batrakoulis, Syaheedah, W., Mohamed, M., Abdulaziz Aldayel, Alhussain, M.H., Hafeez Abiola Afolabi, Wada, Y., Mehmet Gülü, Safaa Elkholi, Bishir Daku Abubakar and Rojas-Valverde, D. (2024). Effects of combined aerobic and resistance training on glycemic control, blood pressure, inflammation, cardiorespiratory fitness and quality of life in patients with type 2 diabetes and overweight/obesity: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *PeerJ*, 12, pp.e17525–e17525. doi:<https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.17525>.

Sarkis-Onofre, R., Catalá-López, F., Aromataris, E. and Lockwood, C. (2021). How to Properly Use the PRISMA Statement. *Systematic Reviews*, 10(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-021-01671-z>.

Scavarda, A., Costa, G. and Beccaria, F. (2021). Using Photovoice to understand physical and social living environment influence on adherence to diabetes. *Health: An Interdisciplinary Journal for the Social Study of Health, Illness and Medicine*, p.136345932110200. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/13634593211020066>.

Schiavenato, M. and Chu, F. (2021). PICO: What it is and what it is not. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 56(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2021.103194>.

Shabibi, P., Abedzadeh Zavareh, M.S., Sayehmiri, K., Qorbani, M., Safari, O., Rastegarimehr, B. and Mansourian, M. (2017). Effect of educational intervention based on the Health Belief Model on promoting self-care behaviors of type-2 diabetes patients. *Electronic Physician*, 9(12), pp.5960–5968. doi:<https://doi.org/10.19082/5960>.

Shah, S.Z.A., Karam, J.A., Zeb, A., Ullah, R., Shah, A., Haq, I.U., Ali, I., Darain, H. and Chen, H. (2021a). Movement is Improvement: The Therapeutic Effects of Exercise and General Physical Activity on Glycemic Control in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Diabetes Therapy*, 12(3). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13300-021-01005-1>.

Shah, V.N. and Garg, S.K. (2015). Managing diabetes in the digital age. *Clinical Diabetes and Endocrinology*, 1(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s40842-015-0016-2>.

Shea, B.J., Reeves, B.C., Wells, G., Thuku, M., Hamel, C., Moran, J., Moher, D., Tugwell, P., Welch, V., Kristjansson, E. and Henry, D.A. (2017). AMSTAR 2: a Critical Appraisal Tool for Systematic Reviews That Include Randomised or non-randomised Studies of Healthcare interventions, or Both. *BMJ*, 358(8122). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j4008>.

Sigal, R., Cep, M., Bacon, S., Boulé, N., Dasgupta, K., Kenny, G. and Riddell, M. (2018). 2018 Clinical Practice Guidelines Physical Activity and Diabetes Diabetes Canada Clinical Practice Guidelines Expert Committee. *Physical Activity and Diabetes*, [online] 42(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcjd.2017.10.008>.

Stuij, M. (2018). 'Physical activity, that's a tricky subject.' Experiences of health care professionals with physical activity in type 2 diabetes care. *BMC Health Services Research*, 18(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-3102-1>.

Trikkalinou, A., Papazafiropoulou, A.K. and Melidonis, A. (2017). Type 2 diabetes and quality of life. *World Journal of Diabetes*, 8(4), p.120. doi:<https://doi.org/10.4239/wjd.v8.i4.120>.

Tugwell, P. and Tovey, D. (2021). PRISMA 2020. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 134, pp.A5–A6. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2021.04.008>.

Viswanadham, N. (2021). Ecosystem model for healthcare platform. *Sādhanā*, 46(4). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12046-021-01708-y>.

Wade, D.T. and Halligan, P.W. (2017). The Biopsychosocial Model of Illness: a Model Whose Time Has Come. *Clinical Rehabilitation*, 31(8), pp.995–1004. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0269215517709890>.

Warburton, D., Jamnik, V., Bredin, S., Shephard, R. and Gledhill, N. (2021). The 2021 Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone (PAR-Q+) and electronic Physical Activity Readiness Medical Examination (ePARmed-X+): 2021 PAR-Q+. *The Health & Fitness Journal of Canada*, 14(1), pp.83–87.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.14288/hfjc.v14i1.351>.

Whelan, M.E., Orme, M.W., Kingsnorth, A.P., Sherar, L.B., Denton, F.L. and Esliger, D.W. (2019). Examining the Use of Glucose and Physical Activity Self-Monitoring Technologies in Individuals at Moderate to High Risk of Developing Type 2 Diabetes: Randomized Trial. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 7(10), p.e14195.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.2196/14195>.

Whitsel, L.P., Ablah, E., Pronk, N.P., Huneycutt, F., Imboden, M.T., Anderson, D., Peterson, N.E., Yocke, S., Sterling, C., Zendell, A.L. and Wojcik, J.R. (2023). Physical Activity Promotion in the Evolving Work Landscape. 37(5), pp.723–730.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/08901171231172013b>.

World Health Organization (2024). *Physical activity*. [online] World Health Organization. Available at:
<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/physical-activity>.

World Health Organization (2018). *More Active People for a Healthier World : Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030*. Geneva: World Health Organization.

Appendix A: PRISMA

Appendix B: Literature Review

Author - Year	Country	Study Design	Sample Size and & Population	Intervention Type	Outcomes Measured	Key Findings
Bennetsen et al. (2020)	Denmark	Systematic Review	12 studies on adults with T2DM	Aerobic, Resistance, Combined	4–24 weeks	HbA1c, CGM variability
Mukherji et al. (2022)	USA	RCT	173 participants with T2DM	Structured group exercise	16 weeks	HbA1c, adherence, body composition
Nery et al. (2017)	Brazil	Metanalysis	12 RCTs, 452 patients	Resistance vs Aerobic	10–20 weeks	Fasting glucose, HbA1c
Al-Mhanna et al. (2024)	Multinational	Systematic Review	30 studies on overweight T2DM patients	Combined training	Varies	HbA1c, BP, CRF, QoL
Kobayashi et al. (2023)	USA	RCT	100 adults with normal-weight T2DM	Strength vs Aerobic	12 weeks	HbA1c, lean mass, fat mass
Avery et al. (2015)	UK	Mixed Methods	Adults with T2DM	Behavioural + aerobic	12 weeks	Glucose control, adherence
Park et al. (2022)	Singapore	Cohort Study	Adults at high risk of T2DM	Lifestyle PA + diet	6 months	CGM glucose levels

Whelan et al. (2019)	UK	RCT	90 participants at risk for T2DM	Wearable tech + PA intervention	8 weeks	PA levels, glucose monitoring
Luoma et al. (2017)	USA	Systematic Review	Studies on practical PA in clinical settings	Various (clinic-based)	Varied	Feasibility, HbA1c, participation rates
Kirwan et al. (2018)	USA	Narrative Review	Multiple studies	General exercise	–	HbA1c, insulin sensitivity
Kanaley et al. (2022)	USA	Consensus Statement	Guidelines-based	All exercise types	–	Consensus guidelines
Colberg et al. (2016)	USA	Position Statement	Expert review	All types	–	Comprehensive review